

Acceptance Letter

To,
Aniket Bhardwaj,

We are pleased to inform you that the research paper / article titled "**A STUDY OF DECLINING CHILDREN'S TELEVISION CONTENT IN INDIA AND ITS IMPACT ON YOUTH**" submitted by you, has been selected for publication in Volume 2 Issue 2 dated 8th April 2026, in **Airo International Journal**.

We wish you a bright research and academic prospects ahead.

Anushka Mishra
Authorized Signatory
Editorial, Airo Journals

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